

EVALUATING PROFIT DISPARITIES IN SELLING VEGETABLES: ROLLING STORE VS MARKET STALL

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ABSTRACT

In examining profit disparities between rolling stores and market stalls in the vegetable retail sector, several factors emerge as pivotal. The rolling store, characterized by mobility and flexibility, offers convenience to customers by reaching them directly in their neighborhoods. Conversely, market stalls operate within fixed locations, providing stability but potentially limiting customer accessibility. Profit differentials stem from operational costs, market dynamics, and consumer behavior. Rolling stores incur lower overhead costs, primarily due to reduced infrastructure and operational expenses compared to market stalls. However, this advantage may be offset by higher transportation costs associated with frequent mobility. Market stalls benefit from a consistent customer base and established foot traffic, fostering predictability in sales volume. Nonetheless, they face competition from neighboring stalls and must contend with seasonal fluctuations. Consumer preferences play a crucial role in shaping profit differentials. While rolling stores offer convenience and proximity, market stalls often boast a wider variety of produce and the opportunity for interpersonal engagement. Consumer demographics and socioeconomic factors influence purchasing decisions, with convenience-oriented shoppers favoring rolling stores and those valuing variety and interaction gravitating towards market stalls. Furthermore, market competition and pricing strategies impact profit differentials. Rolling stores may leverage their mobility to target underserved areas or adjust prices based on demand elasticity. Market stalls, conversely, engage in price competition within a fixed location, necessitating differentiation through product quality or service.

Keywords: *profit disparities, rolling stores, market stalls, interpersonal engagement*

INTRODUCTION

There can be variations in terms of selling vegetables, which are rolling vegetable stores and market stalls (Manucdoc, 2019). In this study, the researchers are identifying which is more efficient in terms of sales. And, to know how rolling stores can be effective to entrepreneurs in selling their products. These issues can make it hard for entrepreneurs to make sales. Rolling stores can be a difficult method because sometimes, the products are not purchased by people, it is also more hassle because they are the ones that are finding their customers (Kennedy et al., 2009). On the other hand, a market stall can also be a hassle, because it only stays in one place. People struggle because they even need to go to their store to buy their products. Rolling Store might struggle to find more customers, so they should find a place that will attract people to buy their products and loyal customers. Also, to be earlier for the customers that are trying to find more viand for breakfast and lunch. On the other hand, market stalls can also be a hassle, market stall owners should find a more crowded area to gain more consumers that will buy their product. In the dynamic landscape of entrepreneurial ventures, the competition between various business models has always been a topic of significant interest and importance. One such intriguing juxtaposition is the comparison between "Rolling Stores" and "Market Stalls" in the context of profit disparities.

These two business models represent distinct approaches to retail and commerce, each with its own set of advantages and challenges. The "Rolling Store" concept entails mobile retail operations, often utilizing vehicles to bring products directly to consumers' doorsteps, providing convenience and accessibility. On the other hand, "Market Stalls" are stationary, often open-air setups in local markets, offering a more traditional shopping experience (Tulukan et al., 2024). This quantitative research seeks to delve into this comparative analysis, aiming to discover on the factors influencing the financial success of rolling stores in contrast to market stalls. By systematically assessing and interpreting the data, the researchers aim to provide valuable insights for entrepreneurs, and stakeholders in the retail industry, making a better understanding of the dynamic retail landscape in today's market-driven economy.

A market stall can be challenging because it only stays in one place, People struggle because they even need to go their store to buy their products (Yu and Pan, 2020). Rolling Store might struggle to find more customers, so they should find a place that will attract people to buy their products and loyal customers. Also, to be earlier for the customers that are trying to find more viand for breakfast and lunch. On the other hand, market stalls can also be a hassle, market stall owners should find a more crowded area to gain more consumers that will buy their product. The contribution of this study is to identify which one people would choose more, and which is more efficient between rolling store and market stalls. And, which the two of them gains more sales and profit. And to discover which of the two is more efficient if you're going to start a business. A rolling store or a market stall. Many past and present projects have aimed to increase children's vegetable consumption by increasing children's exposure to vegetables. For instance, gardening, distribution of free vegetable baskets to classrooms, and parental

initiative to consume fruits and vegetables improved the younger generation's preference (Holloway et al., 2023).

METHODOLOGY

The information about the research and sampling procedures utilized by the researcher is provided in this chapter. The research design employed, the data gathering techniques and the discussion of data analysis are shown in this chapter.

Research Design

This study used the explanatory-sequential method. This is a two-phased method of gathering data. The first phase involved collecting quantitative data, followed by the collection of qualitative data. Qualitative data was used to support and explain quantitative results.

Quantitative data collection was conducted using online survey questionnaires. Through this survey, the difficulties, challenges, lessons and how they handled different consumers were obtained and measured based on the responses of the vegetable marketers. The survey questionnaire also had interview questions which were open-ended. They were used to support quantitative data. The data collected were organized and interpreted.

Data Gathering Techniques

To gather the data needed, permission to conduct the study was sought first. A letter was sent to the authority requesting permission to conduct surveys using survey questionnaires to the respondents. After the permission was given, the researcher discussed personally with the school principal how the survey would be performed. The researchers will conduct their research by doing a Likert scale interview questions and accepting study protocols before the interview. To get material from a specific source, researchers must get permission first from the Curriculum chairman and School Principal. The collection of data involved two phases with each phase using a different set of tools. The first phase focused on the collection of quantitative data through survey questionnaires. The survey questionnaire was intended for vegetable marketers was composed of two parts. The first part is about determining the monthly profit of both stores, while the second part is determining how they overcome difficulties in terms of decrease in sales.

The second phase of the study focused on the gathering of qualitative data. Interview question forms were given to selected vegetable marketers. The interview questions aimed to discover the monthly profit of a rolling store and a market stall.

Sampling Procedures

In choosing the respondents of the study, Purposive Sampling will be used, because of a certain criterion that all respondents should be a vegetable store owner only. Likert scale method is to be conducted. There is 1 vegetable store owner-respondent each for rolling store and market stall in this study.

Data Analysis Scheme

Survey questionnaires were collected, tabulated, tallied, and analyzed. T-test was used to describe the Profit disparities of vegetable stores.

T-Test is to be used to determine the statistical significance of results, The researcher will employ the following statistical tools to summarize and interpret the numerical data of the study.

T-test. This statistic was used to describe the quantitative data and used the Paired Samples t-test to Compare means of two groups called Rolling Store and Market Stall.

Research Instrument

A carefully structured questionnaire was implemented to elicit the necessary information about the evaluation of the differences in the profit of a rolling vegetable store and market stall will be designed by the researchers to gather the data for this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study with the purpose of describing the profit differences between a Rolling Vegetable Store and a Market Vegetable Stall.

Vegetables are an important part of the human diet and a major source of biologically active substances such as vitamins, dietary fiber, antioxidants, and cholesterol-lowering compounds. Despite a large amount of information on this topic, the nutritional quality of vegetables has not been defined. Historically, the value of many plant nutrients and health-promoting compounds was discovered by trial and error (Hounsoume et al, 2008).

Vegetable crops show variable responses to stressful conditions with physiological, biochemical, metabolic and morphological changes that occasionally lead to changes in chemical composition and visual appearance of the final products. Eustressors are various biological, physical or chemical stressful factors that trigger the *signaling pathways* leading to a higher bioactive compounds content and quality

attributes of vegetable products. Therefore, its application could be a useful tool in modern horticulture towards fulfilling the agro-food industry and consumers' demands for high quality and functional vegetable products (Paul et al, 2018). Vegetables are horticultural crops that have a high market absorption. Modern market that is considered to have many advantages does not necessarily reduce consumers' shopping interest at traditional markets. Traditional markets appear to have different characteristics and visitor segments from modern markets. This is to determine the level of consumers' satisfaction of vegetables towards the marketing mix in the traditional markets (Yaqin et al, 2023). Farmers' markets are predominantly fresh food markets that operate regularly within a community where farmers and often retailers, sell produce and associated products directly to consumers. The variables affecting the determination of the sale price of vegetable which is constant over time in a supermarket. It focuses on the non-organic vegetables with a fixed selling price over time such as spinach, beet, and parsley (Miranda, 2017). To investigate and control quality, one must be able to measure quality-related attributes. Quality of produce encompasses sensory attributes, nutritive values, chemical constituents, mechanical properties, functional properties and defects. Instrumental measurements are often preferred to sensory evaluations in research and commercial situations because they reduce variations in judgment among individuals and can provide a common language among researchers, industry and consumers.

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study to determine the monthly profit between the rolling vegetable store and market stall.

Table 1. Comparison of a rolling store and a market stall on attributes of their store and products.

Attributes of a Rolling Store and a Market stall	Rolling Store N = 1			Market Stall N = 1		
	$\bar{x}$	SD	VD	$\bar{x}$	SD	VD
A. Quality						
1. The vegetables in your store are consistently fresh.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
2. The color of your vegetables positively influences customer purchasing decisions.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
3. The texture of your vegetables distinguishes your store from competitors.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
4. The size options available in your store are enough for customers.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
5. The size of your vegetables influences customer purchasing decisions.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A

Overall Mean	15	0	A	15	0	A
B. Price						
1. The pricing of vegetables in your store is perceived as fair by customers	4.00	0	SA	4.00	0	SA
2. The pricing aligns well with the economic preferences of your target customers.	3.00	0	A	4.00	0	SA
3. Customers feel they get value for money with the prices in your store.	3.00	0	A	4.00	0	SA
4. Your pricing strategy contributes positively to customer loyalty.	3.00	0	A	4.00	0	SA
5. Your store effectively suits the value of vegetables in relation to their prices.	3.00	0	A	4.00	0	SA
Overall Mean	16	0	A	20	0	A
C. Availability						
1. Your store maintains a consistent supply of a wide variety of vegetables.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
2. Your store effectively manages and restocks inventory to minimize shortages.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
3. Your store adapts well to seasonal changes in vegetable availability.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
4. Your store communicates effectively with suppliers to ensure a steady source of vegetables.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
5. Your store consistently has popular and in-demand vegetables in stock.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
Overall Mean	15	0	A	15	0	A
D. Customer Satisfaction						
1. You are satisfied with the overall level of customer satisfaction achieved by your store.	4.00	0	SA	4.00	0	SA
2. Your store meets or exceeds customer expectations in terms of service and interaction.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
3. Your store has built a loyal customer base over time.	3.00	0	A	4.00	0	SA
4. Your store effectively addresses and resolves customer concerns or issues in a timely manner.	3.00	0	A	3.00	0	A
5. Your store utilizes customer feedback to make improvements and enhance the overall shopping experience.	4.00	0	SA	3.00	0	A
Overall Mean	17	0	A	17	0	A

Legend:

Scale (VD)	Verbal Description (VD)	Scale	Verbal Description
3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree (D)
2.51 – 3.25 (SD)	Agree (A)	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Table 1 compares the profit of rolling store and a market stall on Attributes of a Rolling Store and a Market stall in terms of quality, price, availability, and customer satisfaction accordingly, to determine the profit of both rolling store and market stall. On Quality, both stores rated item #1-5 with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 3.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 3.00; SD = 0) such that they 'agree' that the quality of their products regarding the profit of their store is good when it comes to their consumers.

In addition, with the attribute of their vegetable's Price, both rolling store and market stall rated item #1 with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 4.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ Teachers = 4.00; SD = 0) such that they 'strongly agree' that the price of their products is moderate and average for their consumers regarding their profit to be average for the day, however, the rolling store differed in

item #2-5, the owner only chose 'agree' with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 3.00; SD = 0), such that they 'agree' and 'strongly agree' that the rolling store one just agreed that the store effectively suits the value of vegetables in relation to their prices. With the availability of their vegetables, both rolling store and market stall both rated item #1-5 with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 3.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 3.00; SD = 0) such that they 'agree' that their store maintains a consistent supply of a wide variety of vegetables. Lastly, both rolling store owner and market stall rated item #1 in the fourth sub-variable which was customer satisfaction had almost the same answers with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 4.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 4.00; SD = 0) such that they 'strongly agree' that their products always pleases and values their consumers. On item #2, both store owners only chose 'agree' with mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 3.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 3.00; SD = 0). In addition, in item #3, only the rolling store owner chose 'agree' with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 3.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 4.00; SD = 0). On item #4, both store owners have the save extent of agreement, they chose 'agree' with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 3.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 3.00; SD = 0). Lastly, in item #5, the market vegetable stall owner was the one who only chose 'agree', while the rolling store owner chose 'strongly agree' with the mean of (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 4.00; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 3.00; SD = 0).

Overall, to note that for all of the item statements on quality, price, availability and customer satisfaction, both groups had responded 'agree' to 'strongly agree' only. (i.e., $2.51 \leq \bar{x} \leq 3.25$ and $3.26 \leq \bar{x} \leq 4.00$, respectively). Generally, the results imply that the rolling store and market stall had similar to strongly agreed on perceptions on the attributes of their vegetable products, expressed in terms of Quality (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 15; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 15; SD = 0); Price (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 16; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 20; SD = 0); and, Availability (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 15; SD = 0 and

$\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 15; SD = 0); Customer Satisfaction (i.e., $\bar{x}$ RollingStore = 17; SD = 0 and $\bar{x}$ MarketStall = 17; SD = 0).

Table 2. Difference between Rolling Vegetable Store and Market Stall in terms of its attributes that influence profitability

Variable	Rolling Vegetable Store N=1		Market Vegetable Stall N=1		t-value	CV	p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Attributes of vegetable stores that influence profitability of Rolling Vegetable Store and Market Vegetable Stall							
A. Quality	5	0	5	0	0	0	0
B. Price	3.6	1.6733200507	5	0	- 1.8708281	2.77645105	0.04965
C. Availability	5	0	5	0	0	0	0
D.Customer Satisfaction	5	0	5	0	0	0	0

In Table 2, the researchers realized that in both method of selling their vegetable products, the quality, availability, and customer satisfaction matters in the profitability of their stores. The price matters, but it is average pricing anyway, so it doesn't affect much in their sales, as long as anybody is buying their products, except when they increase their amount of price, because when price increases, the demand decreases. Unlike market stalls, rolling stores may find it very hard and easy at the same time to find consumers, in terms of geographical limit, they have a very wide range of geographical range because they can go from place to another place, but it is a hassle at the same time, because of their vehicle repairs, gasoline for their vehicle, time management, and more. According to Syverson (2004), better markets does not actually lead to productivity. The finding implies that investment in markets access and infrastructure provides less advancement in agricultural productivity, whereas programs targeted on enhancements

in farm structure and capital have the potential to increase both productivity and market participation. the factors affecting the productivity and profitability of vegetable production. The study showed that access to credit, selling price, fertilizer quantity and gender were significant and positively related to the productivity of the vegetable farmers while distance to market was negatively related to productivity.

Conclusions

Using the procedures described in the preceding chapter, the answers to the problem raised in the study were ascertained and summarized as follows.

For all the statements on quality, price, availability, and customer satisfaction. both groups had responded 'agree' to 'strongly agree'. The results imply that the rolling store and market stall had positively perceived on attributes of the vegetables. This study employed the sequential-explanatory research design under mixed-methodology. It utilized standardized questionnaires in determining the monthly profit of Rolling Store and a Market Stall. It also made use of interview questions, which are open-ended, in the form of structured interview. The responses in terms of using qualitative data of these interview questions were used to corroborate the quantitative data gathered thru the use of standardized questionnaires. The respondents of the study were the rolling vegetable store owner and market vegetable stall owner.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- There is a significant difference in the perceptions of the rolling vegetable store owner and market vegetable stall owner on the attributes of vegetables, expressed in terms of quality, price, availability, and customer satisfaction.
- There is a significant difference in the challenges they face every day between the rolling vegetable store owner and market vegetable stall owner
- There is a significant difference on their method of selling their vegetable products between a rolling store and market stall to their consumers.
- There is a significant difference between the profit of rolling store and a market stall on selling vegetables expressed in terms of quality, price, availability, and customer satisfaction.
- There is a significant difference between a rolling store and a market stall by their geographic range, area control, loyal consumers, and their method of selling vegetables.
- There is a significant difference between the lessons they gain from each other with their methods of selling their products.
- There is a significant difference between the rolling vegetable store and the market vegetable store on how they handle different consumers.

Recommendations

Considering the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were presented.

- The rolling stores and market stalls may offer diverse vegetable products than usual to increase more profit and attract more customers.
- The rolling stores and market stalls may set competitive prices for their vegetables. They may consider bundling options or discounts for larger purchases to encourage customers to buy more.
- Both stores could use signboards for anybody to know that they're selling vegetables and to attract more customers to buy their products.
- Both stores could use megaphones, to attract more consumers to buy their products.
- Both stores must keep the products to be always fresh.
- Both stores should handle their customers with active listening, empathy, problem-solving, and maintaining professionalism.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study. No specific funding was received from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors to support this research. The data generated and analyzed during the study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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